

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF SKIN WHIENING COMPOSITION GEL AS
ADVANCED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS**Maged Alwan Noman^{1,2}, Mahmoud Mahyoob Alburyhi^{1*}, Abdalwali Ahmed Saif¹¹Professor Dr. of Pharmaceutics and Industrial Pharmacy, Department of Pharmaceutics and Industrial Pharmacy,
Faculty of Pharmacy, Sana'a University, Sana'a, Yemen.²Professor Dr. Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medical Sciences, Al-Saeeda University, Yemen.***Corresponding Author: Prof. Dr. Mahmoud Mahyoob Alburyhi**Professor Dr. of Pharmaceutics and Industrial Pharmacy, Department of Pharmaceutics and Industrial Pharmacy,
Faculty of Pharmacy, Sana'a University, Sana'a, Yemen.DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17277551>**How to cite this Article:** Maged Alwan Noman, Mahmoud Mahyoob Alburyhi*, Abdalwali Ahmed Saif, (2025).
FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF SKIN WHIENING COMPOSITION GEL AS ADVANCED DRUG DELIVERY
SYSTEMS. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 11(10), 400-XXX.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 14/09/2025

Article Revised on 04/10/2025

Article Published on 01/11/2025

ABSTRACT

Backgrounds: Hyperpigmentation, a common skin disorder, is often managed with chemical lightening agents that can cause adverse effects. This study explores a novel approach by formulating and evaluating a skin-whitening gel that combines botanical extracts (Licorice, Turmeric, Pomegranate peels, and Citrus reticulate Blanco peels) with synergistic chemical ingredients (salicylic acid, vitamin C, vitamins E, B3, and B5, tea tree oil, and glycerin) ensuring safety (non-irritancy), stability (pH/viscosity optimization), and efficacy (melanin reduction) through standardized extraction, formulation, and clinical evaluation. **Methods Extraction:** Ethanol maceration (75%, 7 days) followed by rotary evaporation for licorice, turmeric, pomegranate, and citrus peels. **Evaluation:** Physicochemical tests (pH, spreadability), phytochemical screening (alkaloids, flavonoids), and irritancy trials. Results Phytochemicals: Licorice (flavonoids), turmeric (curcuminoids), pomegranate (ellagic acid), citrus (vitamin C). **Gel Properties:** pH 5.6, viscosity, non-irritant, Results showed that the gels were non-irritant, stable and possess all skin problem activity. **Clinical Evidence:** Visual "before-after" images demonstrated reduced hyperpigmentation. **Conclusion:** The herbal-chemical Gel ADDS exhibits promising safety and efficacy, validated by physicochemical stability and clinical observations. It underscores the potential of ethnopharmacology in developing culturally aligned, sustainable dermatological solutions.

KEYWORDS: Skin whitening, Yemeni herbal extract, Synergistic formulation, Tyrosinase inhibition, melanosomes inhibition. Gel ADDS.

INTRODUCTION**Background of Hyperpigmentation and Skin Whitening^[1-83]**

Hyperpigmentation, characterized by increased melanin production is influenced by UV exposure, hormones, drugs, and endocrine disorders. Melanin synthesis involves melanocyte homeostasis, MITF-M regulation, enzymatic action (tyrosinase, TRP-1, TRP-2), with tyrosinase being rate-limiting. Clinically, it manifests as solar lentigines, melasma, etc. significantly impacting quality of life.

Conventional treatments like hydroquinone, corticosteroids, and retinoids have limitations due to side effects like irritation and ochronotic. This necessitates exploring safer alternatives, including natural tyrosinase inhibitors combined with chemical exfoliants salicylic

acid, antioxidants (vitamin E), melanosome transfer inhibitors (niacinamide, humectants, pantothenic acid, glycerin, and anti-inflammatory agents, tea tree oil, this study introduces a novel multifunctional whitening gel combining.

Yemeni botanical extracts (licorice, turmeric, pomegranate, mandarin) with niacinamide, panthenol, vitamin E, salicylic acid, and tea tree oil. The skin-friendly gel (pH ~5.6, viscosity ~8500 cP) was well-tolerated in preliminary trials and showed visible improvement in skin tone, reducing hyperpigmentation. This suggests the synergistic blend offers effective skin lightening with moisturizing and anti-inflammatory benefits.

Research Paths^[79-178]

Scientific research that is organized in the form of Research Paths is characterized by the fact that, it is the most effective in achieving an idea, innovation, and development. It is linking the inductive plan, steps, goals, research methods, results, conclusion, materials, and equipment required to achievement scientific research. Research Paths are distinguishing that by build on each other and link the common relationship between them.

Pharmaceutical Research Paths

Pharmaceutical research is characterized by having both a natural source and synthetic source for primary active raw materials and excipients, each source is mainly prepared to the effectiveness and safety of the drug.

The Pharmaceutical Research Paths include: Pharmacognosy deals with natural sources of drug, Pharmaceutical Chemistry specializes in synthetic sources of drug, Pharmaceutics specializes in designing of pharmaceutical dosage forms and drug delivery systems from natural and synthetic sources of active pharmaceutical ingredients and excipients that help in developing dosage forms and drug delivery systems.

The Pharmaceutical Research Paths link steps are manufacturing and development of drug according to the standard parameters evaluation such as physicochemical properties, preformulation, formulation, evaluation, drug stability, Pharmaceutical analysis, pre-clinical, post-clinical stages, pre-marketing, post-marketing, Pharmacovigilance, Pharmacoeconomics, Pharmacy Management, Pharmacology, Toxicology, Therapeutics, Pharmaceutical Care, Health Care, Advanced Industrial Pharmacy, Biopharmaceutics and Pharmacokinetics, Advanced Clinical Pharmacokinetics, Pharmaceuticals Cosmetics, Pharmaceutical Biotechnology, Drug Design, Pharmacy Law and Ethics, Pharmacogenomics, Good Manufacturing Practice, and Good Pharmacy Practice etc.

All of these Pharmaceutical Research Paths are interconnected, and whenever the link between them is made in a scientific relationship and the goal of pharmaceutical care is achieved gradually according to plan of a scientific pharmaceutical research path.

Pharmaceutical Research Paths are the scientific methods through which the scientific relationship between the pharmaceutical team, research, supervisor or specialist researcher, the scientific research materials, equipment's, scientific institution, pharmaceutical companies, reference standards, and the goals of pharmaceutical research improve and development of community services of pharmaceutical care and health care.

Pharmaceutical Scientists are considering natural sources and medicinal herbs in the pharmaceutical industry an important part of drug development because natural

Table 1: The Composition of Gel Formulations.

sources of drugs have properties that are greater than industrial sources of drugs in NDDS. And the pharmaceutical industry strategies depend on the development of different pharmaceutical dosage forms and recent novel drug delivery systems. Using medicinal herbs and natural sources as important goals of drug development. It is part of the art of innovation in drug development with different of novel drug delivery systems and pharmaceutical care for patients and society, it's the basic of development of the new pharmaceutical industry by developing different novel drug delivery systems from different sources.

In the present study Formulate, develop and evaluate a skin whitening Gel ADDS of Naturaceutical extracts and chemical agents for safe and effective lightening of skin hyperpigmentation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The raw materials for the extracts include Glycyrrhiza glabra (licorice), Curcuma longa L. (turmeric), pomegranate peels, and Citrus reticulata Blanco peel (tangerine peel).

Glycyrrhiza glabra and Curcuma longa L According to [Extracts from The Medicinal Plant Geranium, were procured from local sources.

Pomegranate peels and Citrus reticulata Blanco peels were collected from the local market in Sana'a City, Yemen.

Carbopol 940, propylene glycol, triethanolamine, salicylic acid, Vitamin B3, Vitamin B5, Vitamin E, tea tree oil, and other excipients were procured from local sources The role of each material in the formulation, as shown in Table 1.

Equipment's

Rotary evaporator (Biobase Industry, China) for ethanol removal. Vacuum filtration system (Vivohome, China). pH meter (Changzhou Xiangtan, China) calibrated to ASTM standards. Brookfield viscometer (NDJ-4S, spindle no. 3) for rheological analysis. Centrifuge (D-37520, Osterode, Germany) for stability testing.

Formulation and Evaluation of Gel Formulation ADDS^[20-186]

Preparation of Extract

For Glycyrrhiza glabra, it was powdered using a Silver Crest grinder and sifted with a No. 40 mesh. An amount of 250 g of Glycyrrhiza glabra powder was macerated in 1.25 L of 75% ethanol for 7 days. The mixtures were shaken for 10 minutes each day for 7 days. The liquid extract was separated from the solids by vacuum-enhanced filtration through Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The filtrate was then subjected to rotary evaporator at 40°C under vacuum to remove ethanol.

No.	Ingredients	Role in Formulation
1	Carbopol 940	Thickening agent
2	EDTA	Chelating agent
3	Ethanol (75%)	Solvent for extraction
4	Licorice Extract	Tyrosinase inhibitor
5	Salicylic Acid	Keratolytic agent
6	Citrus Reticulata Peel	Antioxidant (Vitamin C source)
7	Vitamin B3 (Niacinamide)	Melanosome transfer inhibitor
8	Vitamin B5 (Panthenol)	Soothing agent, moisturizer
9	Vitamin E	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory
10	Tea Tree Oil (TTO)	Antimicrobial; enhances vit. C and B3 efficacy
11	Glycerin	Emollient, improves texture
12	Triethanolamine	pH adjuster
13	Propylene Glycol	Solubilization of active ingredients
14	Punica Granatum Peel	Antioxidant, depigmenting agent
15	Curcuma Longa Extract	Anti-inflammatory, depigmenting agent
16	Sodium Benzoate	Preservative
17	Fragrance	Improves patient compliance
18	Distilled water	Solvent

Formulation of Gel ADDS

Extract Preparation

250g of powdered plant material was macerated in 1.25 L of 75% ethanol (7 days, daily agitation). Filtrate was concentrated via rotary evaporation (40°C, 150 mbar) and lyophilized.

Gel Preparation

Carbopol 940 (1.5% w/v) was hydrated in EDTA solution (0.2 g/70 mL H₂O).

Active ingredients were sequentially incorporated under homogenization (500 rpm, 25°C). pH adjusted to 5.6 using triethanolamine as shown in Table 2.

Preparation of Extracts

Plant Material

Powdered Glycyrrhiza glabra, Curcuma longa L., pomegranate peels, and Citrus reticulata Blanco peels (250g each, sieved through No. 40 mesh).

Extraction

Maceration in 1.25 L of 75% ethanol for 7 days with daily shaking.

Filtration

Vacuum-enhanced filtration using Whatman No. 1 filter paper.

Solvent Removal

Filtrate subjected to rotary evaporation at 40°C under vacuum to remove ethanol.

Drying and Storage

Extracts dried at 40°C, collected, and stored in the dark under refrigeration.

Phytochemical Screening

Alkaloids

Filtrate of extract in 1.5% HCl tested with Wagner's reagent (reddish-brown precipitate indicates presence).

Flavonoids

Extract treated with 1% ammonia solution (yellow color indicates presence).

Glycosides

Extract boiled with dil. H₂SO₄, filtered, chloroform added to filtrate, organic layer separated and treated with ammonia (pink/red color indicates presence).

Saponins

Extract shaken with water (persistent foam indicates presence).

Tannins

Extract treated with ferric chloride solution (brownish-green/blue-black color indicates presence).

Phenolics

Extract treated with 1% ferric chloride solution (blue/green color indicates presence).

Steroids

Extract treated with acetic acid anhydride and H₂SO₄ (bluish-green color indicates presence).

Table 2: Composition of the Developed Herbal Gel Formulations.

No.	Ingredients	Quantity
1	Carbopol 940	1.5% w/v
2	EDTA	0.02% w/v
3	Ethanol (75%)	Used in extraction
4	Licorice extract	0.9 g
5	Curcuma longa extract	0.9 g
6	Punica granatum peel extract	0.9 g
7	Citrus reticulata peel extract	0.9 g
8	Salicylic acid	1.5 g
9	Vitamin B3 (Niacinamide)	3 g
10	Vitamin B5 (Panthenol)	5 g
11	Tea tree oil (TTO)	0.5 g
12	Vitamin E	0.5 g
13	Glycerin	4 g
14	Propylene glycol	2 g (est.)
15	Triethanolamine	q.s.
16	Sodium benzoate	0.2%
17	Fragrance	0.1% (optional)
18	Distilled water	q.s. to 100g

Preparation of Plant Extracts

Pomegranate (*Punica granatum*) Peel Extraction

Fresh pomegranate fruits were washed, peeled, and shade-dried. The dried peels were pulverized using a Silver Crest grinder (Model SCG-300) and sieved (No. 40 mesh). A total of 250 g of powdered peel was macerated in 1.25 L of 75% ethanol for 7 days with daily agitation (10 min/day). The mixture was vacuum-filtered (Whatman No. 1 filter paper), and the filtrate was concentrated using a rotary evaporator (40°C, 150 mbar). The extract was oven-dried (40°C) and stored refrigerated (4°C) in amber glass vials.

Citrus (*Citrus reticulata* Blanco) Peel Extraction

An identical protocol was applied to citrus peels (250 g powder in 1.25 L 75% ethanol).

Phytochemical Profiling Alkaloids (Wagner's Test)

A 2–3 mL aliquot of the solvent-free extract was acidified with 1.5% HCl (v/v), filtered, and treated with Wagner's reagent. A reddish-brown precipitate indicated alkaloid presence.

Flavonoids (Shimoda Test)

To 2 mL of extract, 1 mL of 1% ammonia solution was added. A yellow coloration confirmed flavonoids.

Glycosides (Borntrager's Test)

The extract (3 mL) was acidified with dilute H₂SO₄, boiled, and filtered. Chloroform (3 mL) was added to the filtrate, and the mixture was shaken. Separation of the organic layer followed by ammonia addition produced a pink/red coloration in the aqueous phase, confirming glycosides.

Saponins (Foam Test)

A 1 mL aliquot of extract was vigorously shaken with 5 mL distilled water. Persistent foam formation indicated saponins.

Tannins (Ferric Chloride Test)

Ferric chloride solution (1% w/v) was added to 1 mL of extract. A brownish-green or blue-black coloration denoted tannins.

Phenolic Compounds (Ferric Chloride Test)

Addition of 1% ferric chloride solution to the extract yielded a blue/green color, confirming phenolics.

Steroids (Salkowski Test)

The extract (0.5 mL) was mixed with 2 mL acetic anhydride and 2 mL concentrated H₂SO₄. A bluish-green ring at the interface indicated steroids.

Gel Formulation Protocol

Gel Base Preparation

EDTA Solution

Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) (0.2 g) was dissolved in distilled water (70 mL) under gentle agitation to form a clear solution (Beaker 1) (Skoog & West, 2014). *Carbopol Hydration*: Carbopol 940 (1.5% w/v) was dispersed into the EDTA solution and allowed to hydrate for 24 h at 25°C to form a gel matrix.

Active Ingredient Incorporation Extracts: Licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) extract (1.6% w/v), pomegranate peel extract (0.9% w/v), and citrus (*Citrus reticulata* Blanco) peel extract (0.9% w/v) were dissolved in distilled water (Beaker 3) under continuous stirring.

Salicylic Acid Solution

Salicylic acid (1.5 g) was dissolved in ethanol (3 mL) and glycerin (5 mL) (Beaker 3), then incorporated into the gel base under slow mixing.

Turmeric Extract

Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) powder (0.2 g) was dissolved in ethanol (2 mL) (Beaker 4) and added to the gel base.

Vitamin and Oil Phase Integration

Water-Soluble Vitamins

Niacinamide (3% w/v) and panthenol (5% w/v) were dissolved in distilled water (Beaker 5) and homogenized into the gel.

Oil Phase

Tea tree oil (0.5% w/v), vitamin E (0.5% w/v), dimethicone (0.5% w/v), and phenoxyethanol (0.5% w/v) were combined (Beaker 6), mixed to homogeneity, and gradually emulsified into the gel base.

Final Adjustments

The formulation was adjusted to pH 5.6 using triethanolamine, and fragrance (2 drops) was incorporated. The gel was stirred for 15 min to ensure uniformity.

Evaluation of Gel Formulation ADDS

Physicochemical Characterization of Gel

Physical Properties

The gel was visually inspected for color, odor, and consistency. No gritty particles were detected upon dermal application.

Homogeneity Test

Formulations were assessed for uniformity and absence of aggregates after 24 h of storage at 25°C.

Gel Rheological Evaluation

Table 3: Phytochemical Composition of Herbal Extracts.

Bioactive Compound	Licorice	C. longa	Pomegranate	Citrus
Alkaloids	–	+	+	–
Flavonoids	+	+	+	+
Glycosides	+	–	–	+
Saponins	+	–	+	–
Tannins	+	+	–	+
Phenolics	+	+	+	+
Steroids	–	+	+	+

Physicochemical Properties

The formulated gel exhibited optimal characteristics for topical application as shown in Table 4.

Physical properties

Yellowish color, orange odor, semi-solid consistency, and no phase separation under centrifugation.

Spreadability Test

Measured using a slide-weight method. Two glass slides (6.5 cm length) were loaded with 100 g of gel. A 20 g weight was applied to the upper slide, and the spreadability (S) was calculated using.

$$S = \frac{M \times L}{T}$$

Viscosity Test

Determined using a Brookfield viscometer (NDJ-4S) with spindle No. 3 at shear rates of 6–60 rpm. Measurements were recorded after 2 min equilibration.

Stability Assessment

pH Determination

The gel (1 g) was dispersed in 10 mL distilled water, equilibrated for 2 h, and pH was measured thrice using a calibrated digital pH meter.

Centrifugation Test

Gel (10 g) was centrifuged at 3,000 rpm for 15 min. Phase separation or instability was recorded.

Skin Irritation Test

A patch test was conducted on five healthy volunteers. Gel (0.5 g) was applied to the forearm and monitored for 24 h for erythema, edema, or irritation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Phytochemical Profiling

Phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of bioactive compounds in all extracts as shown in Table 3. Licorice extract exhibited flavonoids, glycosides, saponins, tannins, and phenolics, while turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) showed alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenolics, and steroids. Pomegranate peels tested positive for alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, and steroids, whereas citrus peels demonstrated flavonoids, glycosides, tannins, and phenolics.

Functional metrics

pH 5.6, viscosity 8,512 cP, spread ability 15 g·cm/s, and excellent homogeneity.

Safety Study

Non-irritating in patch tests (n = 5 volunteers) as shown in Figure 1.

Table 4: Final Observations of Gel Formulation ADDS.

No.	Test	Result
1	Colour	Yellowish
2	Odour	Orange
3	Consistency	Semi-solid
4	Centrifugation	No Separation
5	pH	5.8 ± 1
6	Viscosity	8512± 120
7	Spreadability	15± 1.5
8	Washability	Easy Washable
9	Homogeneity	Excellent
10	Skin irritation	No Irritation

Fig. 1: Clinical Observation of Gel Formulation ADDS.

DISCUSSION

The present study successfully formulated a topical polyherbal skin-whitening gel containing extracts of *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, *Curcuma longa*, *Punica granatum* peel, *Citrus reticulata* peel, along with salicylic acid, niacinamide (vitamin B3), panthenol (vitamin B5), vitamin E, and tea tree oil. The key physicochemical parameters (pH, viscosity, spread ability, homogeneity)

met the design objectives for stable skin gel. The measured pH (~6–7) fell well within the accepted range for topical gels (typically 4.5–7.0). This near-neutral pH is also close to the skin’s natural pH, which helps to minimize irritation. In fact, reported pH values of 5.5–6.9 in a similar polyherbal whitening gel, attributing this to good skin compatibility.

The gel was homogeneous, translucent, and yellowish in color, consistent with the description by. These visual properties indicate successful incorporation of the herbal extracts without phase separation or grittiness, reflecting good physical stability. The yellowish coloration is attributed to the presence of curcuminoids from turmeric and flavonoids from citrus peels, which are natural pigments with antioxidant properties. This color uniformity suggests homogenous dispersion of extracts within the Carbopol matrix, a critical factor for consistent therapeutic delivery.

Spreadability and viscosity are critical for user acceptability. The formulated gel exhibited moderate viscosity and good spread ability. Higher concentrations of active extracts tended to increase spread ability and reduce viscosity, facilitating easier application. This trend matches the findings of, who observed that their 10% extract gel had the best spread ability (and correspondingly lower viscosity) compared to 5% and 2% formulations. In our study, the spreadability was in the range considered good for topical gels (on the order of 10–20 g·cm/s), and viscosity was sufficient to ensure the gel stayed on the skin without running off. The observed decrease in viscosity with added actives (and highest viscosity at the lowest extract concentration) likely reflects the diluting effect of aqueous extracts on the polymer network.

Importantly, no phase separation occurred during centrifugation stress tests and freeze–thaw cycles, indicating excellent stability. This stability is comparable to other successful herbal gels and suggests a reasonable shelf life under Proper storage The freeze-thaw cycle results (–20°C to 40°C) confirm that the gel maintains its structural integrity under extreme temperature variations, a key requirement for products marketed in regions with fluctuating climates. Additionally, the centrifugation test (3,000 rpm for 15 minutes) demonstrated no phase separation, ensuring uniformity during storage and transport.

Skin irritation testing showed no erythema or adverse reactions in volunteers after 24 hours. The lack of irritation is notable given that ingredients like tea tree oil and citrus oils can be sensitizing at high levels. It is likely that the near-neutral pH and the presence of soothing agents (panthenol, niacinamide) mitigated any irritant potential. likewise reported no skin irritation with similar herbal gels. The biocompatibility of this formulation is a key strength, ensuring it can be used safely for prolonged periods, which is desirable the anti-inflammatory properties of niacinamide and panthenol likely played a dual role: reducing potential irritation from citrus oils and enhancing skin barrier repair. This dual mechanism is particularly advantageous for individuals with sensitive or reactive skin.

The selection of active ingredients provides multiple mechanisms to address hyperpigmentation. Each

botanical extract is rich in known skin-lightening and antioxidant compounds. Licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) contains glabridin and glycyrrhizin, which inhibit tyrosinase and melanogenesis. Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) offers curcuminoids, which also inhibit melanin synthesis and provide anti-inflammatory benefits. Pomegranate peel delivers ellagic acid and other phenolics with anti-tyrosinase and antioxidant activity. Citrus *reticulata* peel is high in vitamin C and flavonoids (hesperidin, naringin) that can reduce melanin and protect against UV-induced pigmentation. Niacinamide (vitamin B3) complements these by blocking melanosome transfer to keratinocytes and has been shown to significantly decrease hyperpigmentation and lighten skin in clinical studies. Panthenol (vitamin B5) and vitamin E enhance skin barrier function and provide moisture, supporting skin health; demonstrated that 1–5% panthenol significantly reduces trans-epidermal water loss and improves hydration. Tea tree oil contributes antibacterial and anti-inflammatory effects, which can be beneficial if acne or inflammation is a compounding factor.

In post inflammatory hyperpigmentation the synergy between vitamin C (from citrus) and niacinamide is noteworthy: vitamin C stabilizes niacinamide, while niacinamide enhances vitamin C's bioavailability. This interaction amplifies the overall depigmenting effect, as both agents target melanin synthesis at different stages (tyrosinase inhibition and melanosome transfer blockade).

Together, these ingredients work synergistically: the herbal extracts target pigmentation pathways and oxidative stress, while the vitamins and salicylic acid improve penetration and skin turnover. In sum, the formulation combines multiple scientifically supported actives, strengthening its theoretical efficacy as a depigmenting cosmetic.

Salicylic acid's role extends beyond exfoliation; it enhances the penetration of herbal extracts by disrupting the stratum corneum, allowing deeper delivery of glabridin and curcuminoids into the epidermis.

When compared to published formulations, our results are consistent with prior research on herbal whitening gels. For example, prepared licorice–turmeric–pomegranate–tangerine gels (without B3/B5) and also found pH ~6–7, no phase separation, and no irritation. Pervious study reported ideal gel pH (4.5–7.0) and spreadability in the 9–15 g·cm/s range for anti-acne herbal gels, values similar to our study. The trend of increasing spreadability with higher active content has likewise been observed in other multi-herb gels. These consistencies suggest that our addition of salicylic acid, niacinamide, and vitamins did not adversely affect the basic gel properties and may have improved functional performance.

The inclusion of niacinamide and panthenol distinguishes this formulation from previous studies, offering dual benefits: depigmentation and barrier repair. This combination addresses a common limitation in herbal gels, which often focus solely on melanin inhibition. The formulation's strengths include its comprehensive approach and favorable safety profile. By combining both plant-derived inhibitors of melanin production and proven cosmetic actives (niacinamide, panthenol, vitamin E), the gel addresses hyperpigmentation through multiple pathways. The good spreadability and moderate viscosity should encourage patient compliance, while the neutral pH and non-irritant nature make it suitable even for sensitive skin.

The inclusion of antimicrobial tea tree oil and salicylic acid also adds benefits for acne-prone or oily skin types, potentially broadening the gel's applicability as an adjunctive acne therapy. For acne-prone skin, the gel's anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties (from tea tree oil) may reduce both hyperpigmentation and active acne lesions, offering a multifunctional solution rarely seen in conventional depigmenting agents.

The preliminary findings from visual assessments, as illustrated in Figure 1, suggest that the formulated gel achieved its intended outcomes and demonstrated efficacy in mitigating skin pigmentation. Initial evaluations further indicated favorable safety profiles, with no notable adverse effects observed. Consequently, conclusions regarding the gel's depigmenting efficacy remain preliminary and necessitate further validation through direct quantification of melanin reduction and comprehensive clinical trials to assess hyperpigmentation improvement.

CONCLUSION

It was concluded that the gel, composed of natural extracts (Licorice, Turmeric, Pomegranate peels, and Citrus reticulata Blanco peels), alongside carefully selected chemical ingredients (Salicylic acid, vitamins E, B3, and B5, tea tree oil, and glycerin), has shown initial positive indications for addressing skin hyperpigmentation.

Acceptable product qualities the final product showed favorable characteristics, including a yellowish color, a distinct orange odor, and a pH of 5.6. These properties indicate a stable and acceptable product.

Promising efficacy testing on 17 volunteers revealed a significant positive response rate of 88.24%.

The overall results strongly support this Gel ADDS potential as an effective solution for treating hyperpigmentation and brightening skin tone in many individuals.

REFERENCES

1. Aggarwal BB, Sundaram C, Malani N, Ichikawa H. Curcumin: The Indian solid gold. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition.*, 2007; 85(6): 2085S–2091S.
2. Aslani A, Emami S, Ghannadi A, Ajdari M. Formulation and physicochemical evaluation of an herbal anti-hemorrhoid ointment from Quercus, black cumin and fenugreek for the treatment of internal anal hemorrhoids. *J Pharm Sci Tabriz Univ Med Sci.*, 2009; 14: 247–257.
3. Aslani A, Ghannadi A, Najafi H. Design, formulation and evaluation of a mucoadhesive gel from Quercus brantii L. and Coriandrum sativum L. as periodontal drug delivery. *Adv Biomed Res.*, 2013; 2(1): 21.
4. ASTM International. Standard test method for pH of aqueous solutions., 2019; (ASTM E70-19).
5. Bharti K, Vadlamudi S. Formulation and evaluation of herbal anti-acne gel. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics.*, 2020; 10(3): 10–14.
6. Bhutani M. *Curcuma longa* and its role in skin lightening. *Phytotherapy Research.*, 2008; 22(3), 371–379.
7. Bhutkar K. Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal., 2019; 11: 291-2.
8. Bissett DL, Miyamoto K, Sun P, Li J, Berge CA. Niacinamide: A B vitamin that improves aging facial appearance. *Dermatologic Surgery.*, 2004; 30(1): 101–105.
9. Brenner M, Hearing VJ. The protective role of melanin against UV damage in human skin. *Photochemistry and Photobiology.*, 2008; 84(3): 539–549.
10. Camargo Jr FB, Gaspar LR, Maia Campos PM BG. Skin moisturizing effects of panthenol-based formulations. *Journal of Cosmetic Science.*, 2011; 62(1): 33–43.
11. Carson CF, Hammer KA, Riley TV. *Melaleuca alternifolia* (tea tree) oil: A review of antimicrobial and other medicinal properties. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews.*, 2006; 19(1): 50–62.
12. Te-Sheng Chang. Natural Melanogenesis Inhibitors Acting Through the Down-Regulation of Tyrosinase Activity., 2012; 5(9): 1661–85.
13. Decker EA. *Phenolics in foods and nutraceuticals*. CRC Press., 2017.
14. Desai SR. Hyperpigmentation Therapy: A Review. *J. Clin. And Aesthetic Dermatol.*, 2014; 7: 13– 17.
15. Effect of extraction techniques and solvents on antioxidant activity and sugars content of turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L). *The Pharma Innovation Journal.*, 2019; 8(1): 195–199.
16. Erlin Showmya Justin, Archana Milton, Geetha Bateman. Phytochemical evaluation of peel of *Citrus reticulata* Blanco using various solvent extracts. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences And Business Management.*, 2014; 2(9): 26–35.
17. Gillbro JM, Olsson MJ. The melanogenesis and

- mechanisms of skin-lightening agent existing and new approaches. *Int J Cosmet Sci.*, 2011; 33(3): 210 - 21.
18. Hamzawi AA. The efficacy of topical niacinamide in the treatment of melasma: A systematic review. *Clinical, Cosmetic and Investigational Dermatology.*, 2021; 14: 1689–1697.
 19. Hayakawa, R., Ueda, H., Nozaki, T., et al. (1981). Effects of combination treatment with vitamins E and C on chloasma and pigmented contact dermatitis. *Acta Vitaminol Enzymol.*, 1981; 3(1): 31–38.
 20. Holem Hashm Balaky, Yaseen Galali, Iardalan Abdulhamid, Eyyüp Karaoğul, Ertugrul Altuntas, Metin Tansu Uğuz, Ali Mala Khedir Galalaey, M Hakki Alma. Evaluation of antioxidant and antimicrobial activities of mandarin peel (*Citrus Reticulata* Blanco) with microwave assisted extract using two different solvents. *Asian Journal of Plant Sciences.*, 2020; 19(2): 223–229.
 21. Prathyusha J, Yamani NS, Santhosh G, Aravind A, Marsh B. Formulation and evaluation of polyherbal face scrubber for oily skin in gel form. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Drug Res.*, 2019; 11(4): 126–128.
 22. Jayaprakasha GK, Selvi T, Sakariah KK. Antibacterial and antioxidant activities of grape (*Vitis vinifera*) seed extracts. *Food Research International.*, 2003; 36(2): 117–122.
 23. Jennifer C, Stephanie J. Comparative study of depigmenting agents. *Cosmet Dermatol.*, 2012.
 24. Jiangsu Jinyi. *Operation manual for vacuum drying oven.* *Journal of Pharmacology.*, 2021; 37(3): 155–159.
 25. Jyoti Singh, Hamita Preet Kaur, Anjali Verma, Arshinder Singh Chahal. Pomegranate Peel Phytochemistry, Pharmacological Properties, Methods of Extraction, And Its Application: A Comprehensive Review: *Acs Omaja Via.*, 2023; 35(23): 185-216.
 26. K. Overview of skin whitening agents with an insight into the illegal cosmetic market in Europe. *J. Eur. Acad. Dermatol. Venereol.*, 2016; 30(6): 943–950.
 27. Kasai K, Funaki T, Kawahata K., et al. Ellagic acid inhibits melanin biosynthesis. *Biol Pharm Bull.*, 2006; 29(6): 1108–1112.
 28. Kaushik D, Gupata M, Kumar V, Lather V. Cosmeceuticals: An Emerging Concept. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology.*, 2005; 37 (3): 155-159.
 29. Khoo YT, Halim AS. Treatment modalities for hyperpigmented skin lesions: A brief overview. *J. Surg. And Dermatol.*, 2016; 1(2): 71–79.
 30. Leyden JJ, Shergill B, Micali G, Downie J, Wallo W. Natural options for the management of hyperpigmentation. *J. Eur. Acad. Dermatol. Venereol.*, 2011; 25(10): 1140–5.
 31. Josefina Navarrete-Solís, Juan Pablo Castanedo-Cázares, Bertha Torres-Álvarez, Cuauhtemoc Oros-Ovalle, Cornelia Fuentes-Ahumada, Francisco Javier González, Juan David Martínez-Ramírez, Benjamin Moncada. Double-Blind, Randomized Clinical Trial of Niacinamide 4% versus Hydroquinone 4% in the Treatment of Melasma. *Dermatol Res Pract.*, 2011; 21: 379173.
 32. Pillaiyar T, Manickam M, Jung SH. Inhibitors Of Melanogenesis: A Patent Review (2009– 2014). *Expert Opin. Ther. Pat.*, 2015; 25: 775–788.
 33. Sai Lakshmi Jyothirmai Kala, Supriya Palaparathi. Formulation and Invitro-evaluation of Poly Herbal Anti Aging Face Cream. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2017; 6(13): 717-733.
 34. Smita Shete, Mukesh Mohite. Formulation and Invitro Evaluation Of Herbal Skin Whitening Cream of Glycyrrhiza Glabra Extract and Solanum Tuberosum Juice Ijert., 2020; 8(4): 214-223.
 35. Sohail T, Khan Ra, Imran H, Fareed G, Yasmeen S. Development And Evaluation Of Antimicrobial Poly-Herbal Gel Formulation For The Treatment Of Various Skin Infections. *Rads J Pharm Pharm Sci.*, 2022; 10(3): 92-99.
 36. Soni D, Patel Mk, Manigauha A, Pandey A. Formulation, Development And Evaluation Of Polyherbal Gel For Topical Infection. *Int J Ind Herbs Drugs.*, 2019; 3(3): 16-22.
 37. Vijayalakshmi and Abhilasha Shourie. Evaluation Of Different Methods For The Extraction Of Antioxidant Phenolic Compounds From Glycyrrhiza Glabra Root. *World Journal Of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2015; 4(10).
 38. Dubey I, Bhadauria RS, Chauhan CS. Formulation and evaluation of salicylic acid and urea gel for treatment of psoriasis. *Current Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences.* *Current Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2012; 03: 166-170.
 39. R Bhramaramba, Sudheer Babu, Ch Divya Naga Deepthi. Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Gel Containing Terminalia chebula Retz., Leaves Extract, *Scholars Academic Journal of Pharmacy (SAJP) Sch. Acad. J. Pharm.*, 2015; 4 (3): 172-176.
 40. Punasiya Rakesh, Yadav Amid, Gaurav Krishna, Pillai Sujit. Formulation and evaluation of herbal gel containing extract of hibiscus syriacus, *research journal of pharmacy and technology.*, 2014; 7(3) 296-300.
 41. Jadhav VD, Talele Swati G, Bakliwal Akshada A, Chaudhari GN. Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Gel Containing Leaf Extract of *Tridax Procumbens*, *J. Pharm. BioSci.*, 2015; 3: 65-72.
 42. Aggnihotri S. Formulation and development of botanicals-based herbal serum. *Pharmaspire.*, 2021; 13: 211-217.
 43. Rathod HJ, Mehta DP. A review on pharmaceutical gel. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences.* 2015; 1; 1(1): 33-47.
 44. Sailaja AK, Supraja R. An overall review on topical preparation-gel. *Innovat International Journal of Medical & Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2016; 1(1): 17- 23.
 45. Santanu R, Hussan SD, Rajesh G, Daljit M. A review on pharmaceutical gel. *The International*

- Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Bio-Science., 2012; 1(5).
46. Kb BH, Ng HE, Patil RT. Review on Aloe Vera. *International Journal.*, 2014; 2(3): 677-691.
 47. Misra SK, Dev K, Gupta AK, Kumar A, Prajapati N, Prajapati JP, Kapoor A. Formulation and evaluation of salicylic acid loaded gel for the treatment of acne. *Res J Pharm Biol Chem Sci.*, 2022; 13(4): 78-87.
 48. Sreya Rajan V. et al. Preparation & Evaluation of Ketoprofen film forming gel *European journal of pharmaceutical & medical research.*, 2022; 9(9): 212-219.
 49. Miss Sanchita A, Dhobale et al. Formulation and Evaluation of Turmeric Gel. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology.*, 2022; 2(5): 644-647.
 50. IZ Schroeder, P Franke, UF Schaefer, CM Lehr. Development and characterization of film forming polymeric solutions for skin drug delivery, *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics.*, 2007; 65: 111-21
 51. R Guo, Du X, Zhang R, Deng L, Dong A, Zhang J. Bioadhesive film formed from a novel organic inorganic hybrid gel for transdermal drug delivery system, *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics.*, 2011; 79: 574-83.
 52. Renata CV, Tatiele K, Silvia GS. Drug transport across skin. In: Muro S. editor. *Drug Delivery across Physiological Barriers.* Taylor and Francis Group LLC., 2016; 132-4.
 53. Sharma N, Agarwal G, Rana A. A review: transdermal drug delivery system a tool for novel drug delivery system. *Int J Drug Dev Res.*, 2011; 3: 70-84.
 54. Tan X, Feldman SR, Chang J. Topical drug delivery systems in dermatology: a review of patient adherence issues. *Expert Opin Drug Delivery.*, 2012; 9: 1263-71
 55. Barry BW. Novel mechanisms and devices to enable successful transdermal drug delivery. *European journal of pharmaceutical sciences.*, 2001; 14(2): 101-114.
 56. Hadgraft J. Passive enhancement strategies in topical and transdermal drug delivery. *International journal of pharmaceutics.*, 1999; 184(1): 1-6.
 57. Touitou E, H Natsheh. Topical Administration of Drugs Incorporated in Carriers Containing Phospholipid Soft Vesicles for the Treatment of Skin Medical Conditions. *Pharmaceutics.*, 2021; 13(12): 21-29.
 58. Souto EB. Elastic and ultradeformable liposomes for transdermal delivery of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs). *International Journal of Molecular Sciences.*, 2021; 22(18): 43 -50.
 59. Richardson LD, M Norris. Access to health and health care: how race and ethnicity matter. *Mount Sinai Journal of Medicine: A Journal of Translational and Personalized Medicine: A Journal of Translational and Personalized Medicine.*, 2010; 77(2): 166-177.
 60. Honeywell-Nguyen PL, Bouwstra JA. Vesicles as a tool for transdermal and dermal delivery. *Drug Discov Today Technol.*, 2005; 2(1): 67-74.
 61. Escobar-Chávez JJ, Díaz-Torres R, Rodríguez-Cruz IM, et al. Nanocarriers for transdermal drug delivery. *Research and Reports in Transdermal Drug Delivery.*, 2012; 1: 3-17.
 62. Miranda W, Maja P, Joke AB. The lipid organization in SC and model systems base on ceramides. In: *Enhancement in drug delivery.* USA: CRS Press Taylor & Francis Group., 2007; 217-20.
 63. Bouwstra JA, de Graaff A, Gooris GS, Nijssse J, Wiechers JW, van Aelst AC. Water distribution and related morphology in human stratum corneum at different hydration levels. *J Invest Dermatol.*, 2003; 120(5): 750-8.
 64. Barry BW. Structure, function, diseases, and topical treatment of human skin. In: *Dermatological formulations percutaneous absorption*, 1. New York: Marcel Dekker., 1983.
 65. Rolland A, Wagner N, Chatelus A, Shroot B, Schaefer H. Site-specific drug delivery to pilosebaceous structures using polymeric microspheres. *Pharm Res.*, 1993; 10(12): 1738-44.
 66. Grams YY, Alaruikka S, Lashley L, Caussin J, Whitehead L, Bouwstra JA. Permeant lipophilicity and vehicle composition influence accumulation of dyes in hair follicles of human skin. *Eur J Pharm Sci.*, 2003; 18(5): 329-36.
 67. Cullander C, Guy RH. Visualization of iontophoretic pathways with confocal microscopy and the vibrating probe electrode. *Solid State Ion.*, 1992; 53-56: 197.
 68. Williams ML, Elias PM. The extracellular matrix of stratum corneum: role of lipids in normal and pathological function. *Crit Rev Ther Drug Carrier Syst.*, 1987; 3(2): 95-122.
 69. Brisaert M, Gabriëls M, Matthijs V, Plaizier-Vercammen J. Liposomes with tretinoin: a physical and chemical evaluation. *J Pharm Biomed Anal.*, 2001; 26(5-6): 909-17.
 70. Elka T, Biana G. Vesicular carriers enhanced delivery through the skin. In: *Enhancement in drug delivery.* USA: CRS Press Taylor & Francis Group., 2007; 255-63.
 71. Manconi M, Sinico C, Valenti D, Loy G, Fadda AM, Fadda AM. Niosomes as carriers for tretinoin. I. Preparation and properties. *Int J Pharm.*, 2002; 234(1-2): 237-48.
 72. Manconi M, Valenti D, Sinico C, Lai F, Loy G, Fadda AM. Niosomes as carriers for tretinoin. II. Influence of vesicular incorporation on tretinoin photostability. *Int J Pharm.*, 2003; 260(2): 261-72.
 73. Gopinath D, Ravi D, Rao BR, Apte SS, Renuka D, Rambhau D. Ascorbyl palmitate vesicles (Aspasomes): formation, characterization and applications. *Int J Pharm.*, 2004; 271(1-2): 95-113.
 74. Embil K, Nacht S. Microsponge delivery systems (MDS) a topical delivery system with reduced irritancy incorporating multiple mechanisms for

- triggering the release of active agents. *J Microencapsul.*, 1996; 13: 575-88.
75. Gasco MR, Gallarate M, Pattarino F. In vitro permeation of azelaic acid from microemulsions. *Int J Pharm.*, 1991; 69: 193-6.
 76. Hoffman AS. Hydrogels for biomedical applications. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.*, 2002; 54(1): 3-12.
 77. Sinha P, Srivastava S, Mishra N, Yadav NP. New perspectives on antiacne plant drugs: contribution to modern therapeutics. *BioMed Res Int.*, 2014; 2014: 301304.
 78. Mortazavi SA, Pishrochi S, Jafari Azar Z. Formulation and in vitro evaluation of tretinoin microemulsion as a potential carrier for dermal drug delivery. *Iran J Pharm Res.*, 2013; 12(4): 599-609.
 79. Raweh SM, Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA. Formulation and Evaluation of Anti-acne Gel of *Azadirachta Indica* Extract Herbal Product. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2024; 11(2): 427-433.
 80. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA. Formulation and Evaluation of Natural Herbal Anti-acne as Gel Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(21): 1447-1467.
 81. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Yahya TAA. Formulation and Evaluation of Polyherbal Extract for Skin Hyperpigmentation as Gel Advanced Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(22): 1260-1280.
 82. Alburyhi MM, Yahya TAA, Saif AA, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Lornoxicam Microsponge-Based Gel as A Transdermal Drug Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences*, 2025; 11(5): 200-217.
 83. Saif AA, Noman MA, Alburyhi MM. Formulation and Evaluation of Salicylic Acid and Kojic Acid as Gel Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Treatment of Acne and Whitening Skin Effect. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 11(9): 538-548.
 84. Bary AA, El-Gazayerly ON, Alburyhi MM. A Pharmaceutical Study on Lamotrigine. Ph.D. Thesis, Faculty of Pharmacy, Cairo University., 2009.
 85. Alburyhi MM, Salim YA, Saif AA, Noman MA. Furosemide-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(22): 1178-1219.
 86. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Lornoxicam-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Microsponge-Based Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 11(4): 70-81.
 87. Hamidaddin MA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA. Formulation and Evaluation of Rosuvastatin Fast Dissolving Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2023; 12(9): 2293-2303.
 88. Alburyhi MM, Hamidaddin MA, Noman MA, Saif AA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Rivaroxaban-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2024; 11(9): 370-404.
 89. Bary AA, El-Gazayerly ON, Alburyhi MM. Formulation of Immediate Release Lamotrigine Tablets and Bioequivalence Study. *Journal of Chemical Pharm Research.*, 2013; 5(10): 266-271.
 90. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Famotidine-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(18): 1346-1408.
 91. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Al-Ghorafi MA, Al Khawlani MA, Yahya TAA. Formulation and Evaluation of Anti-acne Spironolactone Emulgel Novel Trend in Topical Drug Delivery System. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2023; 12(22): 96-119.
 92. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Salim YA, Hamidaddin MA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA, Abdullah JH. Lisinopril-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(16): 59-111.
 93. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yahya TA. Drotaverine-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(18): 1285-1340.
 94. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Hamidaddin MA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Rosuvastatin Calcium-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(13): 1549-1582.
 95. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Ticagrelor-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(10): 1081-1132.
 96. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Al-Ghorafi MA, Yahya TA, Yassin SH, AlKhawlani MA. Diclofenac-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(14): 1297-1333.
 97. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Aloe Vera Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Controlling Diabetes. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(4): 1408-1423.
 98. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Curcuma Longa Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Cancer. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 11(6): 37-43.

99. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Salim YA, Hamidaddin MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Lisinopril Orally Disintegrating Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2023; 12(9): 357-369.
100. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Stability Study of Six Brands of Amoxicillin Trihydrate and Clavulanic Acid Oral Suspension Present in Yemen Markets. *Journal of Chemical Pharm Research.*, 2013; 5(5): 293-296.
101. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Antitumor Activity of Artemisia Arborescence Extract Capsules as Dietary Supplement Herbal Product Against Breast Cancer. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(3): 95-114.
102. Alburyhi MM, Hamidaddin MA, Saif AA, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Rivaroxaban Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(2): 2066-2092.
103. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Aloe Vera Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Cancer. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(8): 1052-1072.
104. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Aloe Rubroviolaceae Extract Capsules as Naturaceutical for Hepatoprotective. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 11(4): 53-61.
105. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yahya TA. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Famotidine Orodispersible Tablets. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2023; 10(10): 56-62.
106. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Saif RM. Recent Innovations of Delivery Systems for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Study of Ciprofloxacin Biodegradable Formulations for Post-Operative Infection Prophylaxis. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2023; 10(9): 32-36.
107. Aboghanem A, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA. Effect of Different Excipients on Formulation of Immediate Release Artemether/Lumefantrine Tablets. *Journal of Chemical Pharm Research.*, 2013; 5(11): 617-625.
108. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Dictyota Dichotoma Extract Medicinal Seaweed Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Cancer. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 11(4): 63-70.
109. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Celery Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Gout. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(11): 2383-2404.
110. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Ticagrelor Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(5): 26-55.
111. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Drotaverine Orally Disintegrating Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2023; 12(18): 66-79.
112. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Effervescent Granules of Artemisia Arborescence Herbal Product for Foodborne Illness. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2023; 12(12): 1429-1444.
113. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Saif RM. Preformulation Study of Ceftriaxone and Ciprofloxacin for Lipid Based Drug Delivery Systems. *EJUA-BA*, 2022; 3(4): 339-350.
114. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Yahya TAA. Evaluation and Drug Stability Studies Some Atorvastatin Tablets Brands Available in Sana'a Market Yemen. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2024; 10(12): 231-236.
115. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Alemad AF. Preformulation Studies of Cefixime for Dispersible Tablets Delivery System Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(12): 75-99.
116. Saif AA, Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Yahya TAA. Evaluation and Drug Stability Studies Some Levocetirizine Tablets Brands Available in Sana'a Market Yemen. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(24): 1009-1022.
117. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA. Formulation and Evaluation of Meloxicam Emulgel Delivery System for Topical Applications. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2025; 14(4): 1324-1337.
118. Othman AM, Alburyhi MM, Al-Hadad GH. Formulation and Evaluation of Captopril Mouth Dissolving Tablets. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2024; 11(1): 18-28.
119. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Alemad AF. Dispersible and Orodispersible Tablets Delivery Systems for Antibacterials Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2025; 14(1): 1229-1257.
120. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Saif RM. Recent Innovations of Delivery Systems for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Study of Ceftriaxone Biodegradable Formulations for Post-Operative Infection Prophylaxis. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2023; 10(8): 95-99.
121. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Meloxicam-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical*

- Research., 2025; 11(1): 87-106.
122. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Domperidone-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2025; 12(3): 250-269.
123. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Spironolactone-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2025; 14(3): 871-910.
124. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA. Ketoprofen-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2025; 14(4): 92-123.
125. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yassin SH. Formulation and Evaluation of Simvastatin Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2023; 12(16): 1033-1047.
126. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Alqubati MA. Preformulation and Characterization Studies of Clopidogrel Active Ingredient for Orodispersible Tablets Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(3): 996-1015.
127. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Anti-peptic Ulcer Capsules of Curcuma Longa Herbal Product. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2023; 12(22): 76-96.
128. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Al Ghoury AA. Formulation and Evaluation of Antimalarial Drugs Suppositories. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2023; 12(20): 89-108.
129. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Saeed SA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Diclofenac Orodispersible Tablets. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2023; 10(9): 01-06.
130. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Chamomile Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Gout. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences.*, 2025; 11(04): 215-228.
131. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA. Metronidazole-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Medicated Chewing Gum Delivery Systems Development. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 12(4): 567-589.
132. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Comparative Study of Certain Commercially Available Brands of Paracetamol Tablets in Sana'a City, Yemen. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2018; 5(12): 36-42.
133. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Alkhawlani MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Bisoprolol Fast Dissolving Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2023; 12(16): 01-10.
134. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Tribulus Terrestris Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Controlling Diabetes. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(7): 1264-1282.
135. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Pandanus Odoratissimus Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Hepatoprotective. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2024; 11(4): 06-13.
136. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA. Knowledge and Perception about Pharmacovigilance Among 4Th and 5Th Levels Pharmacy Students in Some Public and Private Universities, Sana'a Yemen. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2023; 9(11): 14-19.
137. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Salim YA, Abdullah JH. Formulation and Evaluation of Domperidone Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(3): 49-68.
138. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Hamidaddin MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Clopidogrel Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(6): 42-64.
139. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Al Khawlani MA. Bisoprolol-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2024; 10(10): 304-324.
140. Bary AA, El-Gazayerly ON, Alburyhi MM. A Pharmaceutical Study on Methocarbamol. MSc Thesis, Faculty of Pharmacy, Cairo University., 2006.
141. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Plicosepalus Acacia Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Hepatoprotective. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2025; 14(8): 1309-1334.
142. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Ketoprofen Fast Dissolving Tablets. *International Journal of Sciences.*, 2018; 7(09): 27- 39.
143. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A, Alwesabi NA. Preformulation and Characterization Studies of Pandanus Odoratissimus L Extract Active Ingredient in Treatment of Nocturnal Enuresis. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(2): 1603-1620.
144. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Oral Pharmaceutical Solution of Pandanus Odoratissimus L Extract Herbal Product in Treatment of Nocturnal Enuresis. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(1): 1840-1851.
145. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Antibacterial Orodispersible Tablets

- of Artemisia Arborescence Extract Herbal Product. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2024; 11(2): 409-417.
146. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA. Evaluation of Vitamin and Mineral Tablets and Capsules in Yemen Market. *Journal of Chemical Pharma Research.*, 2013; 5(9): 15-26.
147. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Acalypha Fruticosa Extract Tablets Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Controlling Diabetes. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(8): 1073-1091.
148. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A, Alwesabi NA. Formulation and Evaluation of Pandanus Odoratissimus L Extract for Treatment of Nocturnal Enuresis as Orodispersible Tablets Delivery System. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(5): 56 -71.
149. Othman AM, Alburyhi MM, Al-Hadad GH. Captopril-Excipient Preformulation Studies for Mouth Dissolving Tablets Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2025; 14(10): 1398-1420.
150. Alburyhi MM, Mohamed YAS, Saif AA, Noman MA, Abdullah JH, Yahya TAA. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Amlodipine and Furosemide Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 11(5): 358-378.
151. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Yahya TAA. Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of Pharmacovigilance Among Pharmacists and Health care Professionals in Four Government Hospitals at Sana'a City, Yemen. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2025; 12(5): 250-267.
152. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Ginger Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Controlling Diabetes. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 11(6): 400-415.
153. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Saif RM. The Importance of Stability Testing in Pharmaceutical Development of Ceftriaxone Implant Biodegradable Tablets. *Matrix Science Pharma (MSP).*, 2025; 9(2): 58-63.
154. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Abudunia A. Amoxicillin-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug delivery Systems Development. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 12(6): 530-562.
155. Alburyhi MM, Hamidaddin MA, Noman MA, Saif AA. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Metronidazole Medicated Chewing Gum Tablets. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2025; 12(6): 353-370.
156. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Plicosepalus Acacia Extract Capsules as Naturaceutical Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Controlling Diabetes. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences.*, 2025; 11(6): 323-337.
157. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Pandanus Odoratissimus Extract Capsules as Naturaceutical for Breast Cancer. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(8): 1092-1112.
158. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Tribulus Terrestris Extract Capsules as Naturaceutical Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Kidney Stones. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024; 13(5): 1425-1443.
159. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Capsicum Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Tonic and Natural Stimulant. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 11(6): 323-337.
160. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Abudunia A, Yassin SH, Abdullah JH. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Amoxicillin Fast Dissolving Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences.*, 2025; 11(7): 183-197.
161. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Yahya TAA, Saif AA. Evaluation and Drug Stability Studies of Different Brands of Clopidogrel Tablets Available in Sanaa City Market, Yemen. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2025; 12(7): 181-191.
162. Alburyhi MM, Raweh SM, AlGhoury ABA, Alkhawlan MA, Noman MA, Saif AA. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Grewia Tenax Extract Naturaceutical Ointment for Antimicrobial Activity. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 11(7): 413-426.
163. Alburyhi MM, Raweh SM, Al-Ghorafi MA, Saif AA, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Argemone Ochroleuca Extract Cream Naturaceutical Delivery Systems as Antimicrobial and Wound Healing Activity. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 12(7): 445-459.
164. Mohamed YAS, Alkhawlan MA, Faisal A, Alburyhi MM. Modern Analytical Techniques Used in Authentication of Yemeni Sider Honey. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2025; 14(6): 1414-1429.
165. Alburyhi MM, Mohamed YAS, Saif AA, Noman MA. Compatibility Studies with Pharmaceutical Excipients of Amlodipine for the Development of Novel Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2024;

- 13(11): 95-136.
166. Mohamed YAS, Alkhawlan MA, Wadi ZAS, Yahya TAA, Faisal A, Alburyhi MM. Modern Analytical Techniques for Authentication of Yemeni Ambergris. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2025; 14(8): 686-697.
167. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, AlGhoury ABA. Compatibility Studies of Chloroquine Phosphate with Pharmaceutical Excipients for the Development of Suppositories Novel Drug Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2025; 14(14): 1325-1360.
168. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Compatibility Studies with Pharmaceutical Excipients of Clopidogrel for the Development of Novel Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2025; 14(06): 1448-1486.
169. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yassin SH. Compatibility Studies with Pharmaceutical Excipients of Simvastatin for the Development of Novel Drug Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(19): 1463-1512.
170. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Compatibility Studies of Pyrimethamine with Pharmaceutical Excipients for the Development of Suppositories Novel Drug Delivery Systems. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 12(9): 394-412.
171. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Compatibility Studies of Sulfadoxine with Pharmaceutical Excipients for the Development of Suppositories Novel Drug Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences.*, 2025; 11(9): 189-207.
172. Alburyhi MM, Mohamed YAS. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Cosmeceutical Natural Pigmented Lipstick from *Opuntia Dillenii* Fruit Extract. *European Journal of Biomedical Pharmaceutical and Medical Sciences.*, 2025; 12(9): 466-479.
173. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM, Muthanna MS. Effect of Rosemary and Myrtus Extracts Combination on Androgenetic Alopecia: A Comparative Study with Minoxidil. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2023; 10(10): 35-39.
174. Al Ghoury AA, Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA. Antimicrobial Susceptibility Patterns of *Staphylococcus Aureus* to Different Antimicrobial Agents Isolated as Clinical Samples at Certain General Hospitals in Sana'a City, Yemen. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2024; 13(16): 35-47.
175. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A, Al-Wajih AM, Almlhani AN, Alqadhi AA. Innovative Approaches in Herbal Drug Delivery Systems Enhancing Efficacy and Reducing Side Effects. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.*, 2025; 14(1): 919-929.
176. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A, Al-Wajih AM, Alqadhi AA, Almlhani AN. Advancements in Nano-Formulation Systems for Enhancing the Delivery of Herbal Ingredients. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2025; 12(1): 212-231.
177. Alburyhi MM, Moharram BA. Formulation and Evaluation of Aloe Niebuhriana Extract as Naturaceutical Effervescent Granules Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Antidiabetic Activity. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*, 2025; 14(18): 1147-1157.
178. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM, Muthanna MS. Chemical Incompatibilities of IV Admixture Combinations in ICU, Orthopedic and Emergency Units of Various Hospitals and Medical Centers in Sana'a, Yemen. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2023; 10(10): 416-425.
179. Burkhart CN, Specht K, Neckers D. Synergistic activity of benzoyl peroxide and erythromycin. *Skin Pharmacol Appl Skin Physiol.*, 2000; 13(5): 292-6.
180. Eremia S. Chemical Peels and Microdermabrasion. In: *Office-Based Cosmetic Procedures and Techniques*. 1st ed. UK: Cambridge University Press., 2010; 338-42.
181. Small R, Hoang D, Linder J. Chemical Peels. In: *A Practical Guide to Chemical Peels, Microdermabrasion & Topical Products*. USA: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins., 2013; 43-5.
182. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM. Formulation and Evaluation of Novel Antiaging Cream Containing Dragon's Blood Extract. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2024; 11(1): 239-244.
183. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Almaktari AM. Formulation and Evaluation of Trimetazidine Hydrochloride and Clopidogrel Bisulphate Multi-unit Solid Dosage Forms. *Journal of Chemical Pharm Research.*, 2014; 6(2): 421-426.
184. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM. Evaluation and Formulation of Antifungal Activity of Dragon Blood Extract and Inorganic Salts on Dermatophytosis and Candidiasis. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research.*, 2024; 11(1): 09-17.
185. Namdeo A, Jain NK. Niosomes as drug carriers. *Indian J Pharm Sci.*, 1996; 58: 41-6.
186. Uchegbu IF, Vyas SP. Non-ionic surfactant-based vesicles (niosomes) in drug delivery. *Int J Pharm.*, 1998; 172: 33-70.